

Preparation of *sym*-Acylarylureas.

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The present work arose from an attempt to study the parallelism in reactions between acetoacetic ester and acetylurethane. The former with aniline gives two classes of products according to the temperature of reaction, an anil (I) and an anilide (II), both of which easily undergo ring-closure with sulphuric acid thus :

Acetylurethane has a similar constitution to β -ketonic ester and behaves analogously with phenylhydrazine as observed by Andreocci (*Gazzetta*, 1889, 19, 448). This led Clark (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1898, 73, 365) to investigate if it also behaves similarly with aniline to form anils and anilides as above, and he found that in all his experiments, although no anil formation could be detected, the anilide was formed. The present work aimed to stretch the analogy a little further by trying to effect a ring-closure in the anilide and thereby synthesise the hitherto unknown methyl- α -quinazolone

The task proved to be very difficult and large quantities of (III) were needed to make an exhaustive attempt, the results of which will be communicated later. Clark's tediously slow process of heating acetylurethane with alcoholic aniline in sealed tubes gave only 60% yield. The yield of acetylurethane by McCreath's process (*Ber.*, 1875, 8, 1182) is also not good. It has been found, however, that acetylurea which can be obtained in a quantitative yield from urea (Werner, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1916, 109, 1127) on heating with aniline at 170° gave acetylphenylurea in good yield. Walther and Wlodkowski prepared this as well as acetyl-*p*-tolylurea and benzoylphenylurea by the action of the acyl chlorides on the arylureas in hot pyridine, but they represented each of them to be unsymmetrical (*aa*-substituted) ureas, $\text{NH}_2 \cdot \text{CO} \cdot \text{N}(\text{R}) \cdot \text{COR}'$. The compounds, prepared in the present investigation, have been found to be identical with Walther and Wlodkowski's compounds and hence their compounds were in fact symmetrical.

After the extraction of acetylphenylurea with hot water a residue was obtained (m. p. 235-36°) which was stable towards boiling acid and alkali and which gave with hot hydrochloric acid traces of aniline. This was identified to be diphenylurea and its production simultaneously with acetylphenylurea suggests that the latter breaks up on prolonged heating into phenyl carbimide which unites with a further molecule of aniline thus:

Acetamide has been isolated in the products of the reaction. The proportion of acetylphenylurea, diphenylurea, acetamide and unchanged acetylurea in the melt was approximately 68.5, 11.4, 14.2 and 5.5% respectively. It may be mentioned here that acetylurea itself is known to decompose on heating to give cyanuric acid. Presumably then, it first decomposes into acetamide and isocyanic acid, the latter polymerising into cyanuric acid.

If the acetamide in the present investigation arose from a primary decomposition of the starting material, a simultaneous formation of monophenylurea ought to result from a condensation of

isocyanic acid with the aniline present. The absence of this and the formation of diphenylurea instead, substantially corroborates the view of the mechanism of reaction previously mentioned.

In the above experiment, aniline was successfully replaced by *p*-toluidine and *p*-anisidine to give yet better yields of *sym*-acetyl-*p*-tolyl and acetyl-*p*-anisylurea. In these cases, the evolution of ammonia was very energetic and the reaction was complete within a much shorter period and if the heating was continued further the yield of acylarylurea was diminished and complex by-products began to appear. Thus acetylurea and *p*-toluidine when heated at 170-75° for 3 hours gave a melt which was practically acetyl-*p*-tolylurea alone but if the heating was continued for 2 hours more, its proportion fell down to 30% with a simultaneous appearance of *p*-ditolylurea.

With *p*-anisidine the effect of heat was still more interesting. Thus at 175-80° for 2 hours, acetylurea and *p*-anisidine gave a melt comprising of 69% of acetyl-*p*-anisylurea, 10% of *p*-dianisylurea and 20% of unchanged acetylurea. If the heating was prolonged for 2 hours more, no unchanged acetylurea could be observed in the melt while the proportion of dianisylurea considerably increased. Curiously further, acetylanisylurea was totally absent and was replaced by two more compounds, one of which was identified to be monoanisylurea and the other had an empirical formula $C_{13}H_{13}O_3N_2$.

In extending the reaction to the case of benzoylurea, all the three amines reacted vigorously to give excellent yields of benzoylarylureas practically without the formation of any by-product. The above method thus proved to be a very easy and quick method for the preparation of symmetrically substituted acylarylureas from cheap starting materials.

EXPERIMENTAL.

Reactions of Acetylurea.

(a) *With aniline.*—Finely powdered acetylurea (5 g.) soaked with aniline (4.5 g.), was heated in an oil-bath at 170-75° for 5 hours, when ammonia was evolved. The melt was poured in a porcelain basin and the solid (9 g.) thoroughly powdered and digested with warm water for a few minutes. The water extract gave on eva-

poration needles of unchanged acetylurea (0.4 g.), which crystallised from alcohol and melted at 217-18°. The alcoholic mother liquor on evaporation gave a viscous oil rapidly solidifying to acetamide (1 g.).

The residue (7.2 g.) was repeatedly extracted with large volumes of boiling water. The acetylphenylurea crystallised in light fern-like mass, m. p. 183°, yield 4.8 g. (Found: N, 15.91. $C_9H_{10}O_2N_2$ requires N, 15.73 per cent). The portion which did not dissolve in hot water was nearly pure diphenylurea. It was obtained from alcohol in small slender needles (0.8 g.), m. p. 235-36°. (Found: C, 73.43; H, 5.66; N, 8.64. $C_{13}H_{12}ON_2$ requires C, 73.58; H, 5.66; N, 8.49 per cent).

(b) *With p-toluidine.*—Equal quantities (3 g.) of both were heated to 215-20° till acetylurea melted and formed a homogeneous mixture. The temperature was then lowered down and maintained at 170° for 5 hours. Finally the temperature was raised to 210° to melt it once more. The acetyl-*p*-tolylurea was extracted with hot water and crystallised from alcohol in needles, m. p. 199-200°, yield 1g. (Found: N, 14.62. $C_{10}O_{12}O_2N_2$ requires N, 14.58 per cent). The residue was ditolylurea (2 g.). It was crystallised from excess of acetone and alcohol, m. p. 260°. (Found: N, 11.92. $C_{15}H_{16}ON_2$ requires N, 11.66 per cent).

In repeating the experiment, the mixture was heated at 170° for 3 hours only. The acetylurea gradually dissolved in the melt and needles separated on the cooler parts. The crude mass on two crystallisations from alcohol gave acetyl-*p*-tolylurea in clusters of needles.

(c) *With p-anisidine.*—The mixture of acetylurea (3 g.) and *p*-anisidine (3 g.) was maintained at 185-90° for 4 hours. The cooled melt was soft and sticky and was digested with hot dilute hydrochloric acid. The extract on adding alkali gave a precipitate which crystallised in plates from water. This was anisidineurea (0.8 g.), m. p. 168°. (Found: N, 16.76. $C_8H_{10}O_2N_2$ requires N, 16.87 per cent). The residue from the dilute acid was crystallised from an excess of alcohol in purple needles, m. p. 220-21°. (Found: C, 64.02; H, 5.62; N, 11.48. $C_{13}H_{13}O_3N_2$ requires C, 63.67; H, 5.30; N, 11.16 per cent). The portion which did not dissolve in alcohol was crystallised from a large excess of amyl alcohol in long flat white needles of dianisylurea, m. p. 235-37°. (Found: N, 10.46. $C_{15}H_{16}O_3N_2$ requires N, 10.29 per cent).

In repeating the experiment the first evolution of ammonia was noticed at 180° and the mixture was maintained at this temperature for 2 hours only. The cooled melt was not sticky and on digestion with warm water for a couple of minutes gave the unchanged acetylurea (1.2 g.). The residue on repeated extraction with boiling water gave a woolly mesh of light needles of acetylanisylurea (4 g.), m. p. 172° . (Found: N, 13.53. $C_{10}H_{12}O_3N_2$ requires N, 13.45 per cent). The undissolved portion was dianisidylurea..

Reactions of Benzoylurea.

Benzoylurea (3.2 g., prepared in a quantitative yield according to the latest improved method of Ostrogovich, *Chem. Zentr.*, 1930, I, 839 and better crystallised from pyridine instead of alcohol in light shining flakes) and aniline (1.8 g.) began to evolve ammonia at 170° . The evolution ceased after $1\frac{1}{2}$ hours and although the mixture was never a complete melt, the flakes of benzoylurea were replaced by minute needles which crystallised beautifully from amyl alcohol in a white mesh but was not pure (3 g.). Glacial acetic acid was a better solvent for purification, m. p. 204.5° . (Found: N, 11.82. $C_{14}H_{12}O_2N_2$ requires N, 11.65 per cent). If the heating was continued till the mixture was nearly a complete melt, the yield was reduced to a quarter and diphenylurea was the chief by-product.

Benzoyl-*p*-tolylurea and benzoyl-*p*-anisidylurea were prepared analogously in excellent yields without by-products, both crystallising from amyl alcohol, m. p. 228.29° and 219° respectively. (Found: N, 11.25. $C_{15}H_{14}O_2N_2$ requires N, 11.02 per cent. Found: N, 10.68; $C_{15}H_{14}O_3N_3$ requires N, 10.37 per cent).

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